

***In-situ* TiO₂/rGO Nanocomposites for CO Detection**

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Abstract

TiO₂ is a well-known wide band gap semiconducting material for gas sensing applications owing to its high temperature stability, chemical stability and high catalytic behavior. However, its low electrical conductivity behavior became an impediment for its practical execution in chemiresistive / conductometric gas sensor (1). Graphene is a two-dimensional zero band gap layered structure which exhibits remarkable electron mobility at the room temperature. Despite, inadequate adsorption characteristics towards gas molecules is a restriction for gas sensing (2, 3). In order to enhance the sensing abilities, the hybridization of TiO₂ and Graphene seems to be an efficient method (4). In the current work, graphene oxide (GO) was synthesized through electrochemical exfoliation method. The TiO₂/rGO nanocomposites were prepared *In-situ* by hydrothermal synthesis using TiCl₃, ammonia and GO (5). XRD and SEM were performed for the microstructural and phase evolution. The sensing properties of TiO₂/rGO composite were investigated in CO environment.

Keywords: TiO₂ Gas sensors, CO detection, TiO₂/rGO composites.

References

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